

Dynamic test of asphalts.

Top Left At the top is placed the pneumatic head and at the bottom the circular sample under test.

Top right. The software allows other configurations beyond the standards ASTM D4123-82:1995 and EN 12697-26:2003.

Bottom left. Details of the LVDTs sensors and the sample support.

Bottom right. Details of the calibration sample mounted on the sample support.

Project description

This machine complies with ASTM D4123-82:1995 and EN 12697-26:2003.

It applies a controlled dynamic (haversine) load to a circular asphalt specimen. The transverse deformation of the specimen is measured using two LVDTs, while the applied load is measured with a load cell.

The load is generated by a pneumatic actuator consisting of a cylinder that converts air pressure and flow into force and displacement. A proportional flow solenoid valve transforms the electrical control signal into regulated airflow. An algorithm was developed to compensate for the nonlinearity in the electrical-to-force transfer function. In addition, the measured load is fed back into the control system to regulate the amplitude of the applied force.

The test is conducted in a temperature-controlled environment ranging from 5 to 40 °C (± 1 °C). This requirement led to the development of a thermally insulated chamber equipped with both refrigeration and heating systems.

An electronic control unit manages the test and communicates with a PC. Force and deformation as functions of time are displayed in real time and recorded for subsequent analysis.